

EFFECTIVENESS OF PSYCHOLOGISTIC APPROACH ON STUDENTS' ACTIVITY

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Abstract. *In this article, it is said that today's student lacks knowledge, that the student should learn from the teacher how to live, and how to get out of problematic situations from the family and school.*

Keywords: *education, child, psycholinguistics, uniqueness of temperaments.*

One of the biggest demands placed on the education of developing countries is the development of learners as competent individuals in all directions in the 21st century. Today's student lacks knowledge. Now the student should learn from the teacher how to live in life and how to get out of problematic situations from family and school. It is known that human learning begins with emotions. Information is conveyed on the basis of verbal and non-verbal communication. Today, the most characteristic progressive trend in the entire science of linguistics, the main topic of psycholinguistic research is the holistic perception of a person. Psycholinguistics is a science that studies the formation of speech, speech perception and processes in the context of their interconnection with the file system; emerged from the synthesis of psychology and linguistics. Psycholinguistics examines the model of human speech activity and the production of psychophysiological speech materials, testing them through practical experiments.

Psycholinguistics, which is close to linguistics in terms of its source of research, is close to psychology in terms of its methods of support. It uses correlation experiment, "semantic differential" and other experimental methods. Psycholinguistics is a series of practical issues [mother tongue, especially teaching the desired language; issues of speech education and speech therapy of preschool children; clinic of diseases of speech centers in the brain; problems of speech influence (especially in the development of vital information and propaganda); forensic psychology and criminology (for example, recognizing and evaluating people based on their quality); appeared in the 60s of the last century due to the theoretical necessity of machine translation and problems of EHM of speech information and others. The term "psychology" refers to the practice of American scientists in the mid-60s of the last century. Although several works have been carried out in this field in Uzbekistan, it still remains one of the directions that have not been fully explored.

In the mainstream of general scientific knowledge, we talk about two interrelated properties: the person himself and the world in which he lives - his essence and existence. A person's connections and relations with the outside world are very diverse, and therefore his characteristics are also diverse. Different forms of activity are often considered in terms of temperamental characteristics. Today, according to the results of both foreign and domestic research, the characteristics of temperament are often called the characteristics of learners, the characteristics that determine the dynamics of their activity, are closely connected and determined by the biological structures of the body. V.D. Nebilitsyn clearly distinguishes temperament from other mental formations of a person. According to him, "temperament in no way describes the

content of a person (worldview, views, beliefs, interests, etc.), does not determine the value of a person or the limits of possible achievements for a particular person. It is only related to the dynamic side of the activity.

The majority of Russian psychologists consider speech as a speech activity, either as an integral activity (if it is a specific impulse not carried out by other types of activity), or as a speech activity included in non-speech activities. The structure of speech activity (or speech act) corresponds to the structure of any movement in general - it includes the stages of orientation, planning (in the form of "internal programming"), implementation and management. Speech activity, like any other activity, is determined by the unity of two sides: external, executive, which carries out its activity and internal, which cannot be observed externally, its organization, planning, programming. Figuratively speaking, a person's speech is a manifestation and continuation of his psychology.

Therefore, studying the possibility of diagnosing temperament characteristics based on the analysis of speech behavior requires a theoretical understanding of the problem and is of great practical importance. The insufficient development of this issue predetermined the purpose, subject, purpose and tasks of this research.

All of the above, according to researchers, the following speech parameters related to the reflection of temperament have the highest information: height (high, medium, low), height range (wide, medium, narrow), pitch level (high, medium, narrow), pitch contour (smooth, recessed, monotonous), direction of tone movement at the end of the phrase (rising - sharp, smooth, flat; falling - smooth, sharp), frequency of addressing the partner, ease of joining the conversation, speed of reaction - answers, pauses, duration of speaking, speed of speech (tempo), volume, variability (variety) of speech, disorder of speech (violation of grammatical structure, semantically) insignificant repetition of phrases, parts of phrases, words, mistakes in design, (neologisms, "swallow" ending), as well as indirect speech semantics.

<p>A "pure" sanguine person (high extraversion and low neuroticism) quickly adapts to new situations, quickly approaches people and is polite. Emotions arise and change easily, and emotional experiences are usually shallow. Mimicry is rich, fast, expressive. He is a little restless, needs new impressions, his impulses are not regulated enough, there is no set order at work, he does not know how to strictly follow the system in life. From this point of view, he cannot distribute energy evenly, he cannot successfully perform a task that requires tension, determination, stability of attention and patience. Without serious goals, he does not think deeply, superficiality and inconsistency develop in creative activity.</p>	<p>Choleric (high extraversion and high neuroticism) is characterized by increased excitability, actions are sporadic. It is distinguished by the tension and hesitancy of actions, strength, vivid expression of emotional experiences. He is inclined to act with all his might when he starts a job. A temperament with the interests of society is manifested in initiative, enthusiasm, and loyalty to principles. In the absence of spiritual life, choleric temperament manifests itself in frequent irritability, inefficiency, lack of self-control, inability to control oneself in emotional situations.</p>
<p>A phlegmatic person is characterized by a relatively low level of behavioral activity,</p>	<p>Melancholy. His reaction often does not correspond to the strength of the stimulus, with</p>

<p>new forms of which develop slowly but are permanent. There is slowness and calmness, equanimity, stability, depth of feeling and mood in movements, facial expressions and speech. A determined and stubborn "worker of life", he rarely loses his temper, is not prone to influence, calculates his strength, brings the matter to the end, even in relationships, a moderate person, idle conversation doesn't like to do. Saves energy, does not waste it. Depending on the circumstances, in some cases, a phlegmatic person has "positive" characteristics - endurance, depth of thought, stability, thoroughness, in others - slowness, indifference to the environment, laziness and lack of will, poverty and weakness of emotions, performing only usual actions desire can be described as high.</p>	<p>their weak expression there is depth and stability of emotions. It is difficult for him to concentrate on one thing for a long time. Strong effects often cause a prolonged intuitive reaction in melancholia (hands down). He is distinguished by restraint and slowness of motor skills and speech, shyness, indecisiveness. Under normal conditions, a melancholic person is a deep, meaningful person, can be a good worker, can successfully complete life's tasks. In unfavorable conditions, he can become a closed, fearful, anxious, vulnerable person, prone to internal experiences that are not at all worthy of such life conditions.</p>
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The mechanism of speech prediction has not yet been fully studied in psycholinguistics. In this case, it is appropriate to use the "models of the future" created by N.A. Bernstein within the framework of the theory of psychophysiological organization of movement. N.A. Bernstein, while researching the emergence and implementation of free movement, shows its sequence in the following stages:

- 1) perception and assessment of the situation;
- 2) to determine what the situation will be as a result of activation;
- 3) what needs to be done for this;
- 4) how to do it.

Thus, any type of speech activity is carried out by means of a complex mechanism. Our thoughts and feelings are expressed in speech. In oral speech, our feelings (emotional experiences) are expressed in word images, tone, rhyme, exclamations and questions, pauses during speaking, and especially intonations. For example, when we call a person by name, we can intentionally or unintentionally express our various feelings and attitudes towards this person: love, anger, pride, love, respect, hatred, contempt, etc. At the same time, the intonation of the speaker expresses his condition, tiredness, general excitement, self-confidence or lack of confidence, and so on.

The results of the experiment obtained from 3-7-year-old children (based on the context of stories, fairy tales) showed that the process of children's reception, the brain of a young child is in an active state when he is told a personally familiar, emotionally significant word. (T. P. Khryzman, V.P. Yermeev, T.D. Loskutov's work "Activity of the child's brain, speech and emotion" is experimentally presented).

In conclusion, it should be noted that every child who receives education is a unique universe. When choosing teaching methods, we must take into account the character and temperament of students. It is worth noting that the teacher who teaches, if he is regularly sought in his field, will definitely achieve success in teaching his subject.

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